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Review Article

A Review On: Cosmetic Preparation, Use of Aloe Vera Gel and Products Available in Market

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ABSTRACT

The Use of Aloe Vera in nutritional, pharmaceutical and cosmetic preparations draw attention for generation of scientific information. In this review paper, different cosmetic preparations and the use of that preparation with products which are available in the market are described. Aloe Vera is an herbal medicine with long traditional use by variety of cultures. The succulent plant grows in arid and subtropical climates. It has been used in traditional and folk medicines for thousands of years to treat and cure a variety of diseases. Although the plant is native to northern parts of Africa, it has rapidly spread across the world because its cultivation is easy. An important distinction has to be made between the strong laxative and purgative latex derived from the bundle sheath cells and clear mucilaginous gel. Aloe Vera is used as an ethno medicine in Trinidad and Tobago for hypertension. The most common folk use of aloe has been for treatment of burn wounds and specifically to aid in healing process.

INTRODUCTION

Aloe Vera – it is nothing but aloe, Ghritkumari, Mussabar obtained from dried juice collected by incision from bases of leaves from aloe *Barbedensis* or aloe *ferox* belongs to family-Liliaceae. Aloe contains crystalline glycosides like aloin 18- 25%, resins 16-37%, emodin, volatile oils etc. Aloe Vera is succulent plant with thick, fleshy, serrated, lanceolate-shaped leaves of green-greyish color. Aloe Vera inner gel is

obtained from the lower leaves of the plant by slicing the leaf open. The gel is clear, odorless, and tasteless and should be free of leaf skin or yellow parts. No consistent standardization has been established. Aloe Vera contains 75 potentially active constituents: vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugar, lignin, saponins, salicylic acids and amino acids. Aloe Vera is rich in vitamin A, C and E which are antioxidants. It also contains vitamin B12, folic acid, and choline. It contains enzymes namely- bradikynin, alkaline phosphates,

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Amylase, catalase, cellulose, peroxidase etc.

Aloe Vera provides various minerals like calcium, potassium, sodium and zinc for proper functioning of various enzyme systems in different metabolic pathways Sugars provide monosaccharides and polysaccharides which are derived from clear mucilage layer of plant and are known as mucopolysaccharides.⁽¹⁾

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection and preparation of plant specimens:

Healthy and mature leaves are taken and rinsed with running tap water to remove the dirt and soil present on it. The leaf and gel separated by peeling skin off with scalpel knife. The mass of gel was dried at room temperature for 18 days. Then the dried mass is pulverized in powder by the use of electric grinder and stored in sealed container until used for photo phytochemical studies.

Phytochemistry of gel extract: The powder is extracted by 100% methanol by continuous hot percolating method in soxhlet apparatus. Then the extract is concentrated in rotary evaporator with brown liquid and kept it in 4°C freezer. The samples were taken out and used for phytochemical screening by standard tests like Wagner's test, borntreger's test. Froth test etc.

Gas chromatography-

Mass spectroscopy analysis. The gel extract samples were send to certified analytical lab to determine the essential oil and fatty acid methanol ester contents of the gel.⁽²⁾

Cosmetological and clinical use of aloe Vera gel:

Hair Aloe Vera can help to treat itchy scalp and flaking skin under the hair. It can also use to treat

seborrheic dermatitis i.e. dandruff. Aloe Vera cleanses the hair shaft efficiently, stripping off extra sebum and residue from other hair products. Aloe Vera gives thickness to the hairs, make soft and shining.⁽³⁾ Acne Aloe Vera can be applied to acne lesion on face and other body parts. It has been reported that the aloe Vera used for wound healing and enhance the healing process of dermal injuries. Aloe Vera is considered as traditional therapy for burns. Aloe Vera is more effective than petroleum jelly gauze dressing, framycetin creams. Aloe Vera can reduce the recovery time, prevent the infection in wound area and prevent the itching and redness of wound. The aloe Vera gel is most effective in 1st and 2nd degree burn wounds than in other degrees. Aloe Vera can also be used for postoperative wounds like episiotomy, cesarean section, skin biopsy and graft.⁽⁴⁾ Preparations of aloe Vera have been used for digestive ailments. Diarrhea and constipation are common issues that may result from irritable bowel syndrome. The aloe leaf innards are rich in plant mucilage and have soothing effect. It contains anthraquinones which helps in constipation but there are some side effects of aloe Vera being too much use.⁽⁵⁾ It was one of most common orthopedic problems occur in patients. Aloe Vera is used for the prevention of pressure ulcer the prevention is control by randomized study triple blind clinical trial in which patients are assigned in 2intervention and control groups. In each group daily cares to prevent bed sores were performed twice a day on areas of hip, sacrum and heel the aloe Vera is rubbed then sacral, hip, and heel of both groups on day 3,8,10 for sign of pressure was evaluated. In intervention group 1 patient afflicted with sore of hip and 2 people with sacral pressure ulcer. In control group 3patient affiliated with sore of hip and 8 people with sacral pressure ulcer and 1 person had pressure sore of heel analysis of data showed that both group have significant difference in incidence of pressure

ulcer which means aloe Vera gel could prevent the pressure ulcer in intervention group.⁽⁶⁾ Herpes simplex virus (HSV) infection is most common oral disease. The aloe Vera gel shows 0.2 - 5% inhibitory effect of HSV in Vero cell line therefore this gel could be useful topical treatment for oral HSV infection without toxicity.⁽⁷⁾

Products Available in Market: ⁽⁸⁾

1. **Lakme:** Creating a soft and hydrated surface for make-up. The formula is light-weight, non-sticky, and extremely effective in preventing the skin from dullness.
2. **Forest essentials:** Enriched with the goodness of rose, organic aloe Vera and cucumber extract, Forest essentials Light Hydrating Aloe Vera Gel is a preferred choice of people with oily skin.
3. **Bio care:** The product prevents the signs of aging and is ideal for both men and women. The best part about this cosmetic is that it will leave your skin moisturized for up to 72 hours.
4. **Khadi:** This gel is a perfect blend of Neem, lavender, camphor extracts, glycerin, and aloe Vera gel. To use, simply apply a small amount of the gel on your face and neck.
5. **VLCC:** It helps to lock the skin moisture and eliminates skin rashes and blemishes. Certain to enhance skin radiance, this gel is made from pure and natural ingredients.
6. **Indus valley:** It penetrates deep into the skin to give it a refreshing glow. Lightweight, non-sticky and pure, this natural formula works effectively to lighten scars and keeps the skin supple and hydrated.
7. **Aroma treasures:** Suitable for all skin types, the Aroma Treasures Aloe Vera Gel is a popular

skin hydrating formula. This gel can be used to treat acne scars, pimples, stretch marks and wounds.

8. **Plum hello aloe gel:** The Plum Hello Aloe Calm This Way Soothing Gel is specially formulated for sensitive skin. The gel helps reduce redness and irritation caused due to breakouts or hair-removal. The product has a cooling light-gel texture, which is organically sourced from aloe juice. This juice provides antioxidant protection. It also soothes the skin. The gel also contains skin-restructuring bio sugars and skin-relieving green tea extract.
9. **Fabindia:** A great natural treatment for nourishing the skin, Fabindia Aloe Vera Gel is one of the best cures for skin burns and wounds.
10. **Patanjali:** The skin brightening solution helps to fight acne and pimples and is suitable for all skin types.

DISCUSSION:

Aloe Vera gel is prepared in which we separate the gel from the leaves by peeling. In extraction process we use Soxhlet apparatus in 100% methanol by continuous hot percolating method. By phytochemical analysis we determine the fatty acids and volatile oils present in aloe Vera. Aloe Vera gel is used for various treatments like acne, eczema for hair dandruff remove. Aloe Vera also used for treatment of obesity, diabetes, skin wound healing, sunburns, tanning of skin. The review describes the use of aloe Vera gel and products available in market.

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